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Categorical characterization of probability product measure
Product probability measure as invariant morphism

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regular conditional probability measure, transition probability.
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Definition (invariant morphism): A morphism g from A to B is said to be an invariant morphism if and only if “for any morphism f from A to A , $g \circ f = g$ ” and “for any morphism h from B to B , $h \circ g = g$ ”. \square

Definition (objects in our category): (X, p) is an object in our category if and only if X is a finite set, p is a map from X to $(0, 1]$ and $\sum_{x \in X} p(x) = 1$. \square

Definition (morphism in our category): $(X \times Y, f)$ is a morphism from (X, p) to (Y, q) if and only if f is a map from $X \times Y$ to $[0, 1]$ such that for any $x \in X$, $\sum_{y \in Y} f(x, y) = p(x)$ and for any $y \in Y$, $\sum_{x \in X} f(x, y) = q(y)$. \square

Definition (composite in our category): For a morphism $(X \times Y, f)$ from (X, p) to (Y, q) and a morphism $(Y \times Z, g)$ from (Y, q) to (Z, r) , let define the composite $(X \times Z, g \circ f)$ as

$$\left\{ \sum_{y \in Y} \frac{f(x, y)g(y, z)}{q(y)} \right\}_{(x, z) \in X \times Z}.$$

\square

Note (reference): I knew the above definition of the category from the online article “Category of joint probability distributions”. \square

Note (measure-preserving mapping, identity morphism): Corresponding

$$\{p(x)\delta_{\sigma(x), y}\}_{(x, y) \in X \times Y}$$

(i.e., the joint distribution obtained from p when x moves to $\sigma(x)$ with probability 1) to a measure-preserving mapping σ from (X, p) to (Y, q) is an embedding functor. In particular, the identity morphism of (X, p) is

$$\{p(x_1)\delta_{x_1, x_2}\}_{(x_1, x_2) \in X \times X}.$$

\square

Proposition (product measure): Let $(X, p), (Y, q)$ be objects. Then,

- (1) $(X \times Y, p \times q)$ is an invariant morphism from (X, p) to (Y, q) .
- (2) If $(X \times Y, f)$ is an invariant morphism from (X, p) to (Y, q) , then $f = p \times q$.

Proof: (1) Easy.

(2) $q \times q$ is a morphism from (Y, q) to (Y, q) , so $f(x, y) = ((q \times q) \circ f)(x, y) = \sum_{t \in Y} \frac{f(x, t)q(t)q(y)}{q(t)} = p(x)q(y)$. \blacksquare

Note (forgetful functor): If F is the functor to the category with finite sets as objects and transition matrices as morphisms, then “ f is invariant” is equivalent to “ $F(f)$ is left-invariant”. \square